

Biginelli reaction

Anil Saini, Sanjay Kumar and Jagir S. Sandhu*

Department of Chemistry, Punjabi University, Patiala-147 002, Punjab, India

E-mail : j_sandhu2002@yahoo.com

Manuscript received 28 May 2007, revised 17 July 2007, accepted 18 July 2007

Abstract : Recent advances in Biginelli reaction are summarized including its latest mechanism, developments in building blocks, catalysts variations, optimization/acceleration of reaction rate using various techniques like microwave irradiation and sonication etc. Also discussed is the reactivity of Biginelli scaffold and some of its modification with a brief note about its outlook.

Keywords : Review Biginelli reaction, catalysis, mechanism, reactivity, microwave.

Hantzsch reaction reported in 1881¹ employs acetoacetic ester, aldehyde and ammonia to produce now well known dihydropyridines or called Hantzsch pyridines **1**. Italian chemist, Pietro Biginelli about a decade later heated same three components acetoacetic ester, benzaldehyde in equimolar ratio, urea (slightly in excess) in alcohol and few drops of conc. hydrochloric acid². He isolated a new compound **2** (now called Biginelli compound and is undoubtedly aza analogue of Hantzsch pyridine) along with small amount of Hantzsch pyridine **1**.

Hantzsch pyridines
(Dihydropyridine)

1

Biginelli compound
(Dihydropyrimidine)

2

Surprisingly, even in the absence of presently available advanced structural elucidation techniques, he correctly assigned the structure **2** to this compound which even today is accepted and established one. In the later years, upto nearly 100 years there were nearly one hundred papers only on this reaction and there were no in-depth studies on this reaction, now commonly called Biginelli reaction³. During these years from its discovery major emphasis was on the substituent variations on the basic structure, scope of the reaction, and some investigation on reaction mechanism. Structural variations were triggered because of its resemblance to commercially used Hantzsch pyridines as antihypertensive agents.

Mechanism :

Folkers and his coworkers⁴ were first to propose a mechanism in 1933 which could remain in practice for some times. Folkers suggestion on the mechanism rested on the postulate that Biginelli three component reaction proceeds through the intermediates **3**, **4** and **5**. Experimentally, they proved under acidic condition; intermediate **5** is not involved; as **3** and **4** could be transformed to **2** and not **5**.

This proposal was further investigated and contrasted by Sweet and Fissekis⁵. According to them the first step is aldol reaction and this is the limiting step in this reaction. Their proposal is outlined in Scheme 1.

It is worth mentioning here that in this reaction dihydropyridines were always formed in minor quantities⁶. Both the above proposal about the mechanism of this reaction left the scope for further investigations which indeed was done by Kappe⁷ based on spectral techniques like ¹H/¹³C NMR spectroscopy. It is pertinent to mention here that the foundation

Scheme 1

of this proposal is purely on spectral data and not either intermediate isolation or conversion etc. (Scheme 2).

According to this mechanism under acidic conditions it is assumed that in the first step, urea molecule acts as nucleophiles to add on to aldehydic carbonyl function, followed by acid catalysed dehydration to afford *N*-acyliminium ion intermediate **8** to which active methylene compound adds in a Michael way. When $\text{CF}_3\text{COCH}_2\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$ was used in place of acetoacetic ester Saloutina and his co-workers could isolate the intermediate **10** and the dehydration is done in the next step using toluene sulfonic acid⁸. This dehydration part in this mechanism is investigated by us also⁹, when GaCl_3 is used as Lewis acid. Support to this comes from the observation that anhydrous GaCl_3 yields Biginelli compounds in excellent yields. In contrast, hydrated GaCl_3 ¹⁰ does not perform well in this reaction.

This addition is also facilitated by acid catalyst and finally

second molecule of water is lost to produce Biginelli compound. In summary, the overall reaction involves two dehydration steps i.e. loss of two water molecules. This mechanism till today remains accepted one as such and is mentioned in several papers published in pursuit of finding convenient conditions and catalyst system to improve the overall process i.e. to achieve high yields and less time. Certainly it can be stated here that no mechanistic studies were further taken. Certainly when one goes from transition metal based catalysts to ammonium salts and others like piperidine, the single mechanism must not be operative and may be different from case to case. Though plethora of catalysts are used including ammonia derived catalysts (see the following pages). Further mechanistic aspects are not investigated and continuing in majority of research papers mechanism is presumed as follows :

Activation of the active methylene compound by a metal salt or transition metal based Lewis acid which would further

Scheme 2

activate the active methylene compound is via a loose complex as shown in A. This complex facilitates addition in a Michael way to *N*-acyliminium ion intermediate 8.

Atwal modification of Biginelli reaction (a two step process) :

The classical Biginelli did not afford the high yields particularly in case of aliphatic aldehydes and aldehydes having slightly hindered carbonyl function by *ortho*-substituents. To overcome some of these problems associated with this method a new approach involving two steps was reported in 1987 by Atwal and his associates¹¹⁻¹³. First step involved separate production of α , β unsaturated carbonyl compound and second step involved the base catalysed addition of substituted ureas as shown in Scheme 3.

Scheme 3

It is pertinent to mention here that this modification of Biginelli reaction have rarely been further investigated in recent years, since it involved two steps.

Biological activities of Biginelli compounds and their impact on further developments in this reaction :

Biginelli compounds show a variety of biological activities. As early as in 1930 their activity to protect wool and woollen clothes was patented¹⁴. As was evident from the structural framework, the Biginelli compounds showed promising antibacterial activity¹⁵. Other promising activity is anti HIV¹⁶ i.e. antiviral activity because of the skeletal resemblance with natural batzelladine alkaloids, viz. batzelladine B.

Other activities worth mentioning here are analgesic¹⁷, anti-inflammatory¹⁸ and specially worth mentioning here is monastrol 12 which has excellent anticancer activity¹⁹.

12

Major synthetic activities for the modifications and simplification in the synthesis have been because of their resemblance with clinically used dihydropyridines as antihypertensive agents²⁰ 13-19. These Biginelli compounds are aza-analogues of Hantzsch pyridines and have shown in

some cases promising calcium channel blocking activity. Hantzsch pyridine readily oxidizes in comparison to Biginelli compounds. Because of this feature these compounds were attracting targets to carry on work to develop as antihypertensive agents. Indeed some success is achieved during past few years and several useful compounds are prepared and are being clinically evaluated, notable ones are SQ 32926, SQ 32547. Other interesting lead compounds, viz. 22, being investigated as anti-hypertensive agents are also at very advanced stage of trials.

11

Batzelladine B

Scope of reaction; investigation/developments in structural variants :

Classically three components are involved in this reaction and fourth is catalyst. Medium employed in this reaction in

the original report is alcohol and temperature used is reflux temperature. As a natural curiosity variations have been investigated to have access to these structurally diverse Biginelli compounds. All these variables are presented in the following pages.

Saini *et al.* : Biginelli reaction

Aldehyde :

Regarding this component, scope of this reaction has been fairly widened as far as possible. Biginelli compounds have been prepared from aliphatic, aromatic and heterocyclic aldehydes²¹ viz. aldehydes 23-40. Typically, scope here have also been extended to aldoses²² and some of their subunits

i.e. aldehydes derived from them like, glyceraldehydes etc. Sugar derived Biginelli compounds are referred to C-nucleosides. Some examples of C-nucleosides thus prepared are shown in 41-43.

Urea :

Regarding urea component, thiourea is very successfully used. As such this variable may be considered as very narrow or restricted; there are not very many variations. Only mono-substituted ureas and thioureas are successfully used^{23,24}. There are also reports of use of guanidine²⁵ but have not been explored in exhaustive way.

Active hydrogen component :

Originally Biginelli used ethyl acetoacetic ester in his historic paper. Over the time several other variations²⁶⁻²⁹ were tried to widen the structure framework of these compounds. Now almost all the conceivable active methylene compounds have been utilized in this reaction. Even then there are major gaps regarding this structural partner which shall be discussed in appropriate section.

Catalyst variations and other related variations leading to products optimizations :

As disclosed above, in the old literature role of catalyst have been critically investigated by Folkers and Johnson⁴.

They did study the optimal use of catalyst and concluded in case of HCl, 8 drops are enough. They seem to be first to use I_2 as catalyst, may be this was clue provided by these authors that in the later years large number of Lewis acid variants have been employed in this transformation by several other workers. May be appearance of authentic account^{30,31} on this reaction or spectrally supported mechanism or the biological significance of these Biginelli compounds has been the cause for tremendous activities in this reaction. Virtually each issue of leading scientific journals published articles on this subject in the recent past. Over the past one decade or so large number of publications dealt with catalyst changes rather than any major structural variations (basic skeleton and variations shall be discussed in later section). To discuss all the catalysts individually used so far, does not seem to be possible/relevant in this account, so it is decided to present important/salient catalyst developments only.

Bronsted acids :

Apart from HCl³²⁻³⁵, many protonic acids like H_2SO_4 ³⁶⁻³⁹, *p*-toluenesulfonic acid^{8,40-42}, methanesulfonic acid⁴³, HBF_4 ⁴⁴, molybdophosphoric acid⁴⁵, phenylboronic acid⁴⁶, PEG- SO_3H ⁴⁷, boric acid⁴⁸ etc. have been used in this reaction.

Lewis acids :

As discussed in the foregoing discussion, oldest use of a Lewis acid dates back to 1933 and it is I_2 ⁴. Certainly, this Lewis acid is readily available, cheap and economical. This may be the reason there are repetitive publications^{49,50} using this catalyst. After these reports iron(III) chloride have attracted major attention of chemists and therefore happens to be subject of various publications⁵¹⁻⁵⁵. The use of $FeCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ has been established to be superior over other Lewis acids by J. Christoffers in Michael reaction in a series of papers/monographs⁵⁶⁻⁶⁰ published by him. From this catalyst onwards large numbers of Lewis acids were developed in this reaction. Virtually each catalyst which did well in Michael reaction proved to be fairly effective in Biginelli reaction, may be one step involved here is that of Michael addition as discussed in mechanism part. Indium metal and its salts fairly dominated the chemical literature during the past several years. Certainly in Biginelli reaction Ranu and co-workers⁶¹ were the first to use $InCl_3$ successfully. Other employed later on different indium salts⁶²⁻⁶⁵. So is the case of $CeCl_3 \cdot 7H_2O$ ⁶⁶, surprisingly which is fairly successful even in water even though reaction involved water elimination in two steps. Other significant Lewis acids to mention are; $BF_3 \cdot Et_2O$ ⁶⁷, $TiCl_4$ ⁶⁸, $ZrCl_4$ ⁶⁹, Cu

salts^{70,71}, ZrO₂⁷², ZnCl₂⁷³, Bi salts⁷⁴⁻⁷⁷, CdCl₂⁷⁸, trimethyl chloride^{79,80}, CoCl₂·6H₂O⁸¹, Mn(OAc)₃·2H₂O⁸², Zn(OTf)₂^{83,84}, Sr(NO₃)₂⁸⁵ and among others notables are, Sm salts^{86,87}, RuCl₃^{88,89}, rare earth triflates^{90,91}, MgBr₂⁹², CaCl₂⁹³, SnCl₂⁹⁴⁻⁹⁷ etc. Another acid combination which has quite often been used is the case of heteropoly acids⁹⁸⁻¹⁰⁵. Virtually all Lewis acids have been used in this reaction. There are certainly metal salts which may not be typically like Lewis acid like LiBr¹⁰⁶, CuSO₄¹⁰⁷ which authors have used successfully. It is noteworthy to mention here LiBr is well precedent to be near neutral¹⁰⁸ salt even then its efficacy is quite good. Among other catalyst system used are ion exchange resin¹⁰⁹, zeolite¹¹⁰, ionic liquids¹¹¹⁻¹¹³. Catalysts like ammonium chloride¹¹⁴, ammonium salts¹¹⁵ and KHSO₄¹¹⁶ have also been used. These catalysts leave scope for further mechanistic investigation. Authors don't find worthwhile to discuss each and every reagents here in this section as it will look superfluous as the references mentioned here itself would reach nearly two hundred.

Biocatalysts :

Very recently an elegant use of fermenting yeast¹¹⁷ and enzyme¹¹⁸ for Biginelli reaction is described. Evidently more work is needed in the use of biocatalysts in this reaction.

Rate enhancement :

In the past sonication and presently microwave irradiations are at the forefront of tools employed for time economy and rate enhancement of organic reactions.

Sonication :

Though sonication of reaction mixture proved quite fruitful and there is large amount of literature is available on this topic, a detailed discussion on this topic is beyond the scope of this account as it is on general organic chemistry. As far as Biginelli reaction is concerned there are only few reports^{119,120} using this technique and catalysts used are Mg(ClO₄)₂ and NH₂SO₃H.

Microwave irradiations :

Gedye¹²¹ introduced the use of domestic microwave oven in organic reaction in 1986. There after, there has been very fast investigation of organic reactions employing this technique and there are several reviews and monographs on this topic¹²²⁻¹²⁹. The use of microwaves in Biginelli is briefly presented in the following lines. The use of microwave in Biginelli reaction is reported by Gupta and co-workers¹³⁰. As far as our survey is concerned this seems to be first ever application in this reaction. Later on microwave is frequently used in this reaction^{8,112,131-141} employing various solvents and otherwise. It is established fact by now solvent-less systems are much safer for microwave irradiations. Certainly

use of solvents is hazardous and in some cases explosions and other problems have been noticed which are clearly mentioned in previous monographs and reviews^{128,129}. In view of this solvent less MWI reaction are more preferred as they are safe. Some selected applications of this solvent less microwave irradiation which are significant and deserve mention here are those using catalysts CuSO₄·5H₂O¹⁰⁷, GaCl₃⁹, polyphosphate ester (PPE)¹⁴¹, Yb(OTf)₃¹⁴².

Miscellaneous processes :

Other improved techniques used in this reaction are fluororous phase¹⁴³⁻¹⁴⁵, solid phase^{146,147} etc.

Biginelli scaffold modifications and Biginelli like reactions :

Oxidation :

It has been mentioned earlier also Biginelli scaffold is not as reactive as Hantzsch pyridines¹⁴⁸, rather it can be said it is inert and if stronger reagents are used for oxidation C₅ substituent is oxidized. The reagents used so far, for oxidation are CrO₃-H₂SO₄¹⁴⁹, SeO₂¹⁵⁰, and electrochemical oxidation¹⁵¹. Some dehydrogenation processes are also known which employ Pd/C¹⁵² and Mn(OAc)₂¹⁵³. Very recently P. T. Perumal and co-workers have described fairly efficient oxidation of this scaffold using ceric ammonium nitrate¹⁵⁴. There are not very many recent investigations on the reduction of Biginelli molecule. If looked carefully in this scaffold C₆ methyl and C₅ substituents are somewhat obstacles in developing the chemistry of this molecule³⁰. Both the substituents are so rigid that these can not be readily functionalised or transformed to other function. When these substituents are not there in the well known oxo-analogue **58** of this molecule C₅-C₆ bond shows the typical character of enamines and excellent chemistry is developed/being developed on this face¹⁵⁵⁻¹⁶¹.

R or R' = H, alkyl, aryl

Oxo-analogue of dihydropyrimidine

In these direction authors and others have made considerable efforts to produce C₅ unsubstituted compounds^{162,163}. These unsubstituted Biginelli compounds are obtained in high yields in three component coupling reaction using aldehyde, urea and aromatic ketones like acetophenone catalysed by AlCl₃/KI system (Scheme 4). The reaction is fairly general i.e. worth mentioning here very nicely authors succeeded in widening the scope of this reaction to common ketones which virtually replaced the traditional active methylene compounds.

Scheme 4

Scheme 5

Scheme 6

Scheme 7

Other important report worth mentioning is C₆ methyl chemistry development by Kamaljit Singh and co-workers¹⁶⁴ (Scheme 5).

Using cycloaddition chemistry, successful manipulation of C₅-C₆ enamine bond of Biginelli compound have recently been reported by Sharma *et al.*¹⁶⁵ (Scheme 6).

Another cycloaddition route to produce unconventional Biginelli compound is reported by Elliott and co-workers¹⁶⁶.

Biginelli like reaction :

When unconventional active methylene compounds like Meldrum's acid, barbituric acid and *N,N*-dimethyl derivative are employed by us¹⁶⁷, the reaction furnishes the spiro-fused heterocycles (Scheme 7).

It is worth mentioning here when aldehydes used here have electron releasing substituents reaction does not proceed

beyond Knoevenagel reaction i.e. does not go upto spiro-heterocyclic production step.

Conclusion :

As one can see Biginelli compounds are highly biologically significant molecules. During the past decade or so the production procedures are so repeatedly reported, there does not seem to be any scope for further preparative refinements. Since Biginelli compounds are now readily available. It is high time to develop the chemistry of basic scaffold which seems to be most appropriate also. Though some initiatives have already been taken during the past few years. Most attractive seems to be application of cycloaddition chemistry inter-, intra- and hetero-cycloaddition which would open up a route to large molecular diversity in Biginelli compounds. After this further fertile area could be investigation on unconventional active methylene compounds.

Lastly the challenging task still left out is the preparation of chiral Biginelli compound as C₄ is the evidently racemic center. Undoubtedly production of chiral drugs is an area of current interest¹⁶⁸.

Acknowledgement

Authors thanks Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi and INSA, New Delhi for financial assistance.

References

- (a) A. Hantzsch, *Ber. Dtsch. Chem. Ges.*, 1881, **14**, 1637; (b) *Justus Liebig Ann. Chem.*, 1882, **15**, 1.
- (a) P. Biginelli, *Ber.* 1891, **24**, 1317; (b) 2962; (c) *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1889, **19**, 212; (d) 1893, **23**, 360.
- (a) W. Kenner and S. Todd, "Pyrimidine and its Derivatives. In *Heterocyclic Compounds*", Vol. 6, ed. R. C. Elderfield, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, 1957, pp. 239-240; (b) H. E. Zaugg and W. B. Martin, in "Org. Reactions", Vol. 14, ed. R. Adams, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, 1965, pp. 88-90.
- K. Folkers and T. B. Johnson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 3784.
- F. Sweet and J. D. Fissekis, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **95**, 8741.
- L. E. Hinkel and D. H. Hey, *Recl. Trav. Chim.*, 1929, **48**, 1280.
- C. O. Kappe, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1997, **62**, 7201.
- V. I. Saloutina, Ya. V. Burgarta, O. G. Kuzuevaa, C. O. Kappe and O. N. Chupakhin, *J. Fluorine Chem.*, 2000, **103**, 17.
- A. Saini, S. Kumar and J. S. Sandhu, *Indian J. Chem.*, (in Press).
- GaCl₃ is commercially available in sealed capsules and absorb moisture as soon as exposed to air.
- B. C. O'Reilly and K. S. Atwal, *Heterocycles*, 1987, **26**, 1185.
- K. S. Atwal, B. C. O'Reilly, J. Z. Gougoutas and M. F. Malley, *Heterocycles*, 1987, **26**, 1189.
- K. S. Atwal, G. C. Rovnyak, B. C. O'Reilly and J. Schwartz, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1989, **54**, 5898.
- W. Hentrich and W. Schepss, (I. G. Farbenind.) D. R. P. 1930, 547, 057 [*Fortsch. Teerfarbenfabr. Verw. Industriezweige* (ed. E. Friedlander), 1932, **25**, 2590].
- T. Matsuda and I. Hirao, *Nippon Kagaku Zasshi*, 1965, **86**, 1195.
- A. D. Patil, N. V. Kumar, W. C. Kokke, M. F. Bean, A. J. Freger, C. Debrossi, S. Mai, A. Truneh, D. J. Faulkner, B. Carte, A. L. Breen, R. P. Hertzbery, R. K. Johnson, J. W. Westley and B. C. M. Potts, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1995, **60**, 1182.
- Y. S. Sadanandam, M. M. Shetty and P. V. Diwan, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 1992, **27**, 87.
- D. Bozong, P. Benko, L. Petocz, M. Szecsey, P. Toempe, G. Gigler, I. Gacsalyi and I. Gyertyan, (EGIS Gyogyszergyar) Eur. Pat. Appl. EP 1991, 409, 233 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1991, **114**, 247302).
- T. U. Mayer, T. M. Kapoor, S. J. Haggarty, R. W. King, S. I. Schreiber and T. J. Mitchison, *Science*, 1999, **286**, 971.
- (a) A. M. Brown, D. L. Kunje and A. Yatani, *Nature*, 1984, **311**, 570; (b) S. F. Flaim and R. Zelis, *Fed. Proc.*, 1981, **40**, 2877.
- (a) H. Taguchi, H. Yazawa, J. F. Arnett and Y. Kishi, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1977, 627; (b) R. Hull and G. Swain, GB Patent 868, 030/1958 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1958, **56**, 7729).
- (a) A. Dondoni, A. Massi and S. Sabbatini, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2001, **42**, 4495; (b) F. J. Lopez Aparicio and F. J. Lopez Herrera, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1979, **69**, 243.
- H. Namazi, Y. R. Mirzaei and H. Azamat, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 2001, **38**, 1051.
- A. Dandia, M. Saha and H. Taneja, *J. Fluorine Chem.*, 1998, **90**, 17.
- J. J. Vandenn Eynde, N. Hecq, O. Katacva and C. O. Kappe, *Tetrahedron*, 2001, **57**, 1785.
- T. Chiba, H. Sato and T. Kato, *Heterocycles*, 1984, **22**, 493.
- K. K. Mayer, S. Dove, H. Pongratz, M. Ertan and W. Wiegrebe, *Heterocycles*, 1998, **48**, 1169.
- G. Y. Remennikov, *Chem. Het. Compounds (New York)*, 1997, **33**, 1369 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1998, **129**, 216523).
- S. Sarac, M. Yarim, M. Ertan, S. Boydag and K. Erol, *Pharmazie*, 1998, **53**, 91 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1998, **129**, 230344).
- C. O. Kappe, *Tetrahedron*, 1993, **49**, 6937.
- (a) C. O. Kappe, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 2000, **33**, 879; (b) *Molecules*, 1998, **3**, 1; (c) *J. Med. Chem.*, 2000, **35**, 1043.
- Y.-F. Chi and Y.-C. Ling, *Sc. Sinica*, 1957, **VI**, 247.
- R. Hull and G. Swain, GB Patent 868,030/1958 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1958, **56**, 7729).
- M. K. Jani, N. K. Undavia and P. B. Trivedi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **67**, 847.
- D. Bozong, P. Sohar, G. Gigler and G. Kovaes, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 1996, **31**, 663.
- E. H. Hu, D. R. Sidler and U. H. Dolling, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1998, **63**, 3454.
- P. Salehi, M. Dabiri, M. A. Zolfigol and M. A. B. Fard, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2003, **44**, 2889.
- P. Salehi, M. Dabiri, M. A. Zolfigol and M. A. B. Fard, *Heterocycles*, 2003, **60**, 2435.
- Z. Hassani, R. M. Islami and M. Kalantri, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2006, **16**, 4479.
- C. O. Kappe, S. F. Falsone, W. M. F. Fabian and F. Belaj, *Heterocycles*, 1999, **51**, 77.
- T. Jin, S. Zhang and T. Shung, *Synth. Commun.*, 2002, **32**, 1847.
- A. K. Bose, M. S. Manhas, S. Pednekar, S. N. Ganguly, H. Dang, W. He and A. Mandadi, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2005, **46**, 1901.
- T. S. Jin, H. X. Wang, C.-Y. Xing, X.-L. Li and T.-S. Li, *Synth. Commun.*, 2004, **34**, 3009.
- W. Y. Chen, S. D. Qin and J. R. Jin, *Catalysis Commun.*, 2007, **8**, 123.
- M. M. Heravi, K. Bakhtiari and F. F. Bamoharram, *Catalysis Commun.*, 2007, **8**, 373.
- A. Debache, B. Boumoud, M. Amimour, A. Belfaitah, S. Rhouatia and B. Carboni, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2006, **47**, 5697.

47. X. Wang, Z. Quan, F. Wang, M. Wang, Z. Zhang and Z. Li, *Synth. Commun.*, 2006, **36**, 451.
48. S.-J. Tu, X.-T. Zhu, F. Wang, X.-J. Zhang, S.-L. Zhu, T.-J. Li, D.-Q. Shi, X. S. Wang and S.-J. Ji, *Chin. J. Chem.*, 2005, **23**, 596.
49. R. S. Bhosale, S. V. Bhosale, T. Wang and P. K. Zubaidha, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2004, **45**, 9111.
50. K. V. N. S. Srinivas and B. Das, *Synthesis*, 2004, 2091.
51. L. Jun, Y. J. Bai, Z. L. Wang, B. Yang and H. R. Ma, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2000, **41**, 9075.
52. L. Jun and M. Huairang, *Synlett*, 2000, 63.
53. L. Jun and B. Yinjuan, *Synthesis*, 2002, 466.
54. I. Cepriec, M. Litvic, A. Bartolincic and M. Lovric, *Tetrahedron*, 2005, **61**, 4275.
55. I. S. Zorkun, S. Sarac, S. Celbi and K. Eral, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2006, **14**, 8582.
56. J. Christoffers, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1* 1997, 3141.
57. J. Christoffers, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.*, 1998, 1259.
58. J. Christoffers, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1998, **39**, 7083.
59. J. Christoffers, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.*, 1998, 759.
60. (a) J. Christoffers, H. Oertling and M. Leitner, *Synlett*, 2000, 349; (b) J. Christoffers, Several personnel communication and exchange of views.
61. B. C. Ranu, A. Hajra and U. Jana, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2000, **65**, 6777.
62. N.-Y. Fu, Y.-F. Yuan, Y. Cao, S.-W. Wang, J.-T. Wang and C. Feppe, *Tetrahedron*, 2002, **58**, 4801.
63. N.-Y. Fu, Y.-F. Yuan, M.-L. Pang, J.-T. Wang and C. Feppe, *J. Organometallics Chem.*, 2003, **672**, 52.
64. M. A. P. Martins, M. V. M. Teixeira, W. Cunico, E. Scapin, R. Mayer, C. M. P. Pereira, N. Zanatta, H. G. Bonacorso, C. Peppe and Y.-F. Yuan, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2004, **45**, 8991.
65. R. Ghosh, S. Maiti and A. Chakraborty, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Chem.* 2004, **221**, 137.
66. D. S. Bose, L. Fatima and H. B. Mereyala, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2003, **68**, 587.
67. A. Dondoni, A. Massi and S. Sabbatini, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2001, **42**, 5917.
68. R. R. Nagawade, S. A. Kotharkar and D. B. Shinde, *Mendeleev Commun.*, 2005, **4**, 150.
69. C. V. Reddy, M. Mahesh, P. V. K. Raju, R. Babu and V. V. N. Reddy, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2002, **43**, 2657.
70. H. R. Kalita and P. Phukan, *Catal. Commun.*, 2007, **8**, 179.
71. A. S. Paraskar, G. K. Dewkar and A. Sudalai, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2003, **44**, 2757.
72. V. Singh, V. Sapehiyia, V. Srivastav and S. Kaur, *Catal. Commun.*, 2006, **7**, 571.
73. Q. Sun, Y.-Q. Wang, Z.-M. Ge, T.-M. Cheng and R. T. Li, *Synthesis*, 2004, 1047.
74. R. Varala, M. M. Alam and S. R. Adapa, *Synlett*, 2003, 67.
75. Y. T. Reddy, B. Rajitha, P. N. Reddy, B. Sunil and V. P. Rao, *Synth. Commun.*, 2004, **34**, 3821.
76. K. Ramalinga, P. Vijayalakshmi and T. N. B. Kaimal, *Synlett*, 2001, 741.
77. M. M. Khodaei, A. R. Khosropour and M. Jowkar, *Synthesis*, 2005, 1301.
78. A. V. Narsaiah, A. K. Basak and K. Nagaiah, *Synthesis*, 2004, 1253.
79. Y. Zhu, Y. Pan and S. Huang, *Synth. Commun.*, 2004, **34**, 3167.
80. S. V. Ryabukhin, A. S. Plaskon, E. N. Ostapchuk, N. Eugenyi, D. M. Volochnyuk and A. A. Tolmachev, *Synthesis*, 2007, 417.
81. S. Kumar, A. Saini and J. S. Sandhu, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2005, **44**, 762.
82. K. A. Kumar, M. Kasthuraiah, C. S. Reddy and C. D. Reddy, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2001, **42**, 7873.
83. H. Xu and Y. G. Wang, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2003, **43**, 2604.
84. H. Xu and Y. G. Wang, *Chinese J. Chem.*, 2003, **21**, 327.
85. C. Liu, J. Wang and Y. Li, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Chem.*, 2006, **258**, 367.
86. X. Fan, X. Zhang and Y. Zhang, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 2002, 436.
87. X. Han, F. Xu, Y. Luo and Q. Shen, *Eur. J. Org. Chem.*, 2005, **8**, 1500.
88. S. K. De and R. A. Gibbs, *Synthesis*, 2005, 1301.
89. S. L. Jain, V. B. Sharma and B. Sain, *J. Het. Chem.*, 2006, **43**, 777.
90. B. Desai, D. Dallinger and C. O. Kappe, *Tetrahedron*, 2006, **62**, 4651.
91. R. Ghosh, S. Maiti and A. Chakraborty, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Chem.*, 2004, **217**, 47.
92. H. Salehi and Q.-X. Guo, *Chinese J. Chem.*, 2005, **23**, 91.
93. B. Gangadasu, P. Narender and B. C. Raju, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2006, **45**, 1259.
94. S. Kumar, A. Saini and J. S. Sandhu, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2004, **43**, 1485.
95. D. K. Roy and M. Bordoloi, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2006, **45**, 1067.
96. M. Shailaya, A. Manjula, B. V. Rao and N. Parvathi, *Synth. Commun.*, 2004, **34**, 1559.
97. D. Russowsky, F. A. Lopes, Victo S. S. de Silva, K. F. S. Canto, M. G. M. D'Oca and M. N. Godoi, *J. Braz. Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **15**, 165.
98. S. P. Maradur and G. S. Gokavi, *Catal. Commun.*, 2007, **8**, 279.
99. K. Niknam and N. Daneshvar, *Heterocycles*, 2007, **2**, 373.
100. M. M. Amini, A. Shaabani and A. Bazgir, *Catal. Commun.*, 2006, **7**, 843.
101. E. Rafiee and H. Jafari, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2006, **16**, 2463.
102. E. Rafiee and F. Shahbazi, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Chem.*, 2006, **250**, 57.
103. B. G. Mishra, D. Kurnar and V. S. Rao, *Catal. Commun.*, 2006, **7**, 457.
104. D. S. Bose, M. V. Chary and H. B. Mereyala, *Heterocycles*, 2006, **68**, 1217.

105. M. A. Chary and K. Syamasundear, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Chem.*, 2004, **221**, 137.
106. P. P. Baruah, S. Gadhwal, D. Prajapati and J. S. Sandhu, *Chem. Lett.*, 2002, 1038.
107. M. Gohain, D. Prajapati and J. S. Sandhu, *Synlett*, 2004, 235.
108. H. Firouzabadi, B. Karimi and S. Eslami, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1999, **40**, 55; (b) H. Firouzabadi, N. Iranpoor and B. Karimi, *Synthesis*, 1999, 58.
109. J. K. Joseph, S. L. Jain and B. Sen, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Chem.*, 2006, **247**, 99.
110. M. Tajbakhsh, B. Mohajerani, M. M. Heravi and A. N. Ahmadi, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Chem.*, 2005, **236**, 216.
111. M. Li, W.-So Guo, L.-R. Wen, Y.-F. Li and H.-Z. Yang, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Chem.*, 2006, **258**, 133.
112. J.-C. Legeay, J. J. V. Eynde and I. P. Bazureau, *Tetrahedron*, 2005, **61**, 12386.
113. Z.-T. Wang, S.-C. Wang and L.-W. Xu, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 2005, **88**, 986.
114. A. Shaabani, A. Bazgir and F. Teimouri, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2003, **44**, 857.
115. K. R. Reddy, Ch. V. Reddy, M. Mahesh, P. V. K. Raju and V. V. N. Reddy, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2003, **44**, 8173.
116. S. Tu, F. Fang, S. Zhu, T. Li, X. Zhang and Q. Zhuang, *Synlett*, 2004, 537.
117. A. Kumar and R. A. Maurya, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2007, in press (doi: 10.1016/j.tetlet.2007.04.130).
118. B. Schnell, W. Krenn, K. Faber and C. O. Kappe, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 2001, 4382.
119. X. Zhang, Y. Li and C. L. J. Wang, *J. Mol. Catal. A : Chem.*, 2006, **253**, 207.
120. J.-T. Li, L.-F. Han, J.-H. Yang and T.-S. Li, *Ultrasonic Sonochem.*, 2003, **10**, 119.
121. R. Gedye, F. Smith, K. Westaway, H. Ali, L. Baldisera, L. Laberge and J. Rousell, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1986, **27**, 279.
122. C. O. Kappe and D. Dallinger, *Nat. Rev. Drug. Discovery*, 2006, **5**, 55.
123. W. D. Shipe, S. E. Wolkenberg and C. W. Lindsley, *Drug Discovery Today : Tech.*, 2005, **2**, 155.
124. E. Leadbeater, *Chem. Commun.*, 2005, 2881.
125. C. O. Kappe, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2004, **43**, 6250.
126. Y. Xu and Q. X. Guo, *Heterocycles*, 2004, **63**, 903.
127. J. Hamelin, J. P. Bazureau and F. Taxier-Boullet, in "Microwaves in Organic Synthesis", ed. A. Loupy, Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, 2002, p. 253.
128. P. Lidstrom, J. Tierney, B. Wathey and J. Westman, *Tetrahedron*, 2001, **57**, 9225.
129. L. Perreux and A. Loupy, *Tetrahedron*, 2001, **57**, 9199 and references cited therein.
130. R. Gupta, A. K. Gupta, S. Paul and P. L. Kachroo, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1995, **34**, 151.
131. R. Gupta, S. Paul and A. K. Gupta, *Indian J. Chem. Technology*, 1998, **5**, 340.
132. C. O. Kappe, D. Kumar and R. S. Varma, *Synthesis*, 1999, 1799.
133. A. Stadler and C. O. Kappe, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 2000, 1363.
134. H. A. Stefani and P. M. Gatti, *Synth. Commun.*, 2000, **30**, 2165.
135. M. Xia and Y.-G. Wang, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2002, **43**, 7703.
136. S. J. Tu, J. F. Zhou, P. J. Cai, H. Wang and J. C. Feng, *Synth. Commun.*, 2002, **32**, 147.
137. S. E. Mallakpour, A. R. Hajipour, K. Faghihi, N. Foroughifar and J. Bagheri, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 2001, **80**, 2416.
138. S. Xue, Y.-C. Shen, Y.-L. Li, X.-M. Shen and Q.-X. Guo, *Chinese J. Chem.*, 2002, **20**, 385 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 2002, **137**, 169482).
139. V. R. Chaudhary, V. H. Tillu, V. S. Narkhede, H. B. Borate and R. D. Wakharkar, *Catalysis Commun.*, 2003, **4**, 449.
140. M. S. Manhas, S. N. Ganguly, S. Mukherjee, A. K. Jain and A. K. Bose, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2006, **47**, 2423.
141. C. O. Kappe, O. V. Shinshkin, G. Uray and P. Verdino, *Tetrahedron*, 2000, **56**, 1859.
142. Y. Ma, C. Qian, L. M. Wang and M. Yang, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2000, **65**, 3864.
143. A. Studer, S. Hadida, R. Ferritto, S. Y. Kim, P. Jeger, P. Wipf and D. P. Curram, *Science*, 1997, **275**, 823.
144. A. Studer, P. Jeger, P. Wipf and D. P. Curram, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1997, **62**, 2917.
145. M. G. Valverde, D. Dallinger and C. O. Kappe, *Synlett*, 2001, 741.
146. A. Dondoni and A. Massi, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2001, **42**, 7975.
147. C. O. Kappe, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2000, **10**, 49.
148. (a) A. Sausins and G. Duburs, *Heterocycles*, 1988, **27**, 291; (b) A. Saini, S. Kumar and J. S. Sandhu, *Synth. Commun.*, 2007, **37**, 2317.
149. V. A. Slavinskaya, G. Duburs, D. Sile, D. Kreile and E. L. Knanina, USSR Patent 1978, 632 695 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1979, **90**, 121631).
150. E. L. Khanina and G. Duburs, *Khim. Geterotsikl. Soedin.*, 1982, 535.
151. (a) V. Kadis, J. Stradins, E. L. Khanina, G. Duburs and D. Muceniecc, *Khim. Geterotsikl. Soedin.*, 1985, 117; (b) V. Kadis, J. Stradins, E. L. Khanina and G. Duburs, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1989, **34**, 899.
152. C. O. Kappe and P. Roschger, *J. Het. Chem.*, 1989, **26**, 55.
153. M. S. Akhtar, M. Seth and A. P. Bhaduri, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1987, **26**, 556.
154. P. Shanmugam and P. T. Perumal, *Tetrahedron*, 2006, **62**, 9726.
155. P. J. Bhuyan, R. C. Borah and J. S. Sandhu, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1990, **55**, 568.
156. P. J. Bhuyan, J. S. Sandhu and A. C. Ghosh, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1996, **37**, 1853.
157. P. J. Bhuyan, K. C. Lekhok and J. S. Sandhu, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1999, **40**, 1793.
158. P. J. Bhuyan, H. N. Borah and J. S. Sandhu, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin*

- Trans. J.*, 1999, 3083.
159. P. J.. Bhuyan, H. N. Borah and J. S. Sandhu, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2002, **43**, 895.
160. M. Noguchi and N. S. Kajigaeshi, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1986, **34**, 3994.
161. H. Koroniak, P. Katwatka and T. Cytlak, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2004, **45**, 5767.
162. A. Saini, S. Kumar and J. S. Sandhu, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2006, **45**, 684.
163. Z. -T. Wang, L.-W. Xu, C.-G. Xia and H.-Q. Wang, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2004, **45**, 7951.
164. K. Singh, S. Singh and A. Mahajan, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2005, **70**, 6114.
165. P. Sharma, A. Kumar, N. Rane and V. Gurram, *Tetrahedron*, 2005, **61**, 4237.
166. M. C. Elliott, E. Kruiswijk and D. J. Willock, *Tetrahedron*, 2001, **57**, 10139.
167. A. Saini, S. Kumar and J. S. Sandhu, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2004, **43**, 2482.
168. For recent review see; Sangita and S. Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **83**, 315.